

Environmental Chemistry

Development of a reliable preprocessing protocol for fluorescent micro- and nanoplastic analysis in human placental tissue

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Abstract

Concerns are arising about potential health risks of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) to human life, as their presence has been reported in human blood, stool, liver, lung tissue, breast milk, and placenta. However, little is known about particle numbers and morphology, which is essential information for developing reliable risk assessment. Therefore, such characterization of MNPs in human tissue is an important yet difficult task, which involves sample digestion as an essential step in the pretreatment of organic matrices. Successful digestion enables accurate characterization of MNPs using micro-spectroscopy. In this study, eight different enzymes or enzyme mixtures commonly used in digestion protocols were tested in four different buffers, to select the best combinations of enzymes and buffers for the preprocessing of human placental tissue for MNP (spectro-)microscopic analysis. Placenta tissue was spiked with fluorescent 200 nm, 500 nm, 1 μ m, and 10 μ m polystyrene (PS) MNPs to analyze morphological stability throughout the digestion and to determine recovery rates (RRs). For the optimal protocol, RRs of 98% \pm 6 (200 nm), 148% \pm 8 (500 nm), 147% \pm 8 (1 μ m), and 81% \pm 8 (10 μ m) were determined using confocal fluorescence microscopy (CFM). We explain values >100% by dye leaching and hypothesize that the leached dye can bind to organic residue from tissue with a similar size as the fluorescent PS particles, causing false positives when counting MNPs. Morphological changes were not observed for the final digestion protocol both with CFM and scanning electron microscopy. Hence, we demonstrate an optimized enzymatic digestion protocol to digest (placental) tissue and report on the accuracy of the characterization of model MNPs using micro-spectroscopy, which will enable further research with an emphasis on sub-micron (<1 μ m) sized plastic particles.

Keywords: micro- and nanoplastics, fluorescence microscopy, biological tissues, digestion protocol

Introduction

Of the 8.3 billion metric tons of plastic produced from the 1950s until now, 79% has ended up in our environment. Only 9% of all plastic waste is being recycled (Geyer et al., 2017). When being discarded into the environment, plastic may also end up in rivers and in the ocean, where it is exposed to UV light and water, which eventually break it down into microplastics or even smaller nanoplastics (Koelmans et al., 2015). The terms micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are still under debate, but microplastics are generally referred to as particles <1 mm and nanoplastics as particles <1 μ m (Gigault et al., 2018; International Organization for Standardization, 2020).

Micro- and nanoplastics are being detected in many food matrices, as well as in drinking water (Alexander et al., 2016; Alimi et al., 2018; Hernandez et al., 2019; Horton et al., 2017; Liebezeit & Liebezeit, 2014; Rios Mendoza et al., 2018; Ter Halle et al., 2017). The question arises whether they are also present in the human body and recent studies suggest they are. Leslie et al.

(2022) have found that MNPs >700 nm are present in the human bloodstream (Brits et al., 2024). Ragusa et al. (2021, 2022a, 2022b) have found microplastics in the human placenta and in human breast milk. Microplastics were detected both in the maternal and fetal side of the placenta, inside the intracellular compartment (Ragusa et al., 2022a). Still, only a handful of particles could be detected, and proper identification of individual particles' plastic species remains extremely challenging.

Both in vitro and ex vivo studies have shown that polystyrene (PS) MNPs, as well as other nanoparticles, can be taken up by placental cells (Bongaerts et al., 2020; Dusza et al., 2022; Grafmueller et al., 2015; Walczak et al., 2015). The placenta regulates fetal growth and development, by providing the fetus with nutrients and oxygen, making it an important matrix in understanding MNPs' health effects for the unborn child. It is also known that MNPs can act as "Trojan horses" by binding and releasing environmental pollutants, such as metals, metalloids, and particulate matter, that may have an adverse health effect

Received: March 5, 2025. Revised: May 22, 2025. Accepted: June 25, 2025

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on the developing fetus (Hildebrandt et al., 2021; Malmqvist et al., 2013; Su et al., 2020; Wojtyla et al., 2020). Furthermore, a protein corona can be formed around MNPs, thereby influencing MNPs' uptake and toxicity. It has been shown that the composition of this corona influences the placental transfer of PS particles (Gruber et al., 2020). The composition of this corona could be altered by any chemicals used during the sample processing method, which further emphasizes the importance of checking the influence of the sample processing method on MNPs' uptake and toxicity. The extent to which uptake takes place is dependent on particle size, with smaller-sized particles being taken up more easily (Dusza et al., 2022; Walczak et al., 2015). Because still little is known about the type of particles, their morphological properties (such as particle size, shape, and surface chemistry) and particle numbers present in placental tissue, further research is essential to develop a more accurate risk assessment of MNPs for the unborn child (Christopher et al., 2024).

To date, pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry is dominantly used to quantify MNPs, but this analytical technique does not provide any information about particle size, shape, or number (Shao et al., 2025). Besides, biological matrices, like placental tissue, show interference from fat tissue breaking down into similar pyrolysis products as found for polyethylene (Rauert et al., 2022; Witzig et al., 2020). Interferences like these increase the limit of detection and limit of quantification of certain polymer types, thereby complicating the analysis of light-weight NPs. Therefore, the use of (spectro-)microscopic techniques is an important addition in the establishment of such a risk assessment (Mandemaker & Meirer, 2023).

However, to detect MNPs in human tissue using (micro-)spectroscopic techniques, the tissue must first be chemically broken down, ideally without altering the MNPs present. Since both plastics and human tissue primarily consist of carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen, micro-spectroscopy cannot rely on elemental composition differences for contrast (such as available via electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray analysis). Instead, selective tissue digestion is required. Additionally, placental blood may need to be removed from the tissue sample to determine whether MNPs originate from maternal blood or are present within placental cells. Current research focuses on developing optimized digestion protocols for analyzing MNPs in human (placental) tissue.

An option to digest organic matrices is enzymes, which are very selective catalysts. For example, a protease will only break down proteins, whereas strong bases and acids may break down both proteins and plastics (Hurley et al., 2018; Karami et al., 2017; Löder et al., 2017; von Friesen et al., 2019). The amide bond in proteins will be broken down by proteases, whereas the amide bond in polyamide will not be attacked as proteases only cut in between specific amino acids. Several enzymes are being used in digestion protocols in literature. Lipase is known to digest lipids, that are present in the cellular membrane. Proteinase K, trypsin, and pepsin are three different types of proteases that digest proteins. Trypsin cleaves at the C-terminus of Arg and Lys, proteinase K at the C-terminus of aliphatic and aromatic amino acids, and pepsin cleaves at the C-terminus of hydrophobic amino acids. Proteinase K has a wider variety of amino acids cleavage sites than trypsin and pepsin and is therefore widely used in digestion protocols (Correia & Loeschner, 2018; Karlsson et al., 2017; Leslie et al., 2022; Thiele et al., 2019). Pancreatin is a mixture of pancreatic enzymes, containing among others lipase, protease, and amylase, that digests starch. Collagenase digests collagen, that is present in the extracellular matrix. Benzonase

nuclease digests DNA and RNA, which is present in the cell nucleus. Accutase is a mixture of protease and collagenase.

Even though these enzymes should in principle not digest MNPs, it is important to check for the stability of MNPs throughout digestion and throughout the conditions used during digestion (temperatures, homogenization, etc.), as the methodology should not lead to physico-chemical changes in MNPs. In literature, stability tests are done either by measuring weight change on a filter or by microscopic images of particle morphology (Catarino et al., 2017; Courteney-Jones et al., 2017; Hurley et al., 2018; Karami et al., 2017; Löder et al., 2017; Stock et al., 2020). With environmentally relevant concentrations of MNPs, recovery rates (RRs) in terms of particle numbers could however be more useful than weight changes, as a change in mass is difficult to measure at low concentrations and small particle sizes. Additionally, weight changes do not contain any information on particle morphology. Therefore, a combination of change in particle number and change in morphology would be ideal to assess the stability of MNPs throughout a digestion protocol.

As visually represented in Figure 1, the study aimed to develop a digestion protocol suitable for human placental tissue by using eight enzymes or enzyme mixtures commonly used in tissue digestion protocols. Fluorescent PS (FPS) beads were added to the matrix before digestion, in known concentrations and particle numbers. These FPS functioned as an internal standard to calculate the particle RR. Fluorescent PS particles were analyzed with confocal fluorescence microscopy (CFM), which was used as a validation tool to study FPS particle morphology and allows for determining RRs. This work thus presents a critical view on CFM as an MNP characterization tool, as well as a protocol and a toolbox to study particulate matter in human placental tissues enabling future assessment of MNPs in the field of early-life risk assessment.

Materials and methods

Sample collection

A placenta was voluntarily donated from a healthy delivery at term (>38 weeks). Participant provided written informed consent under regulations within the Netherlands and maintained by the ethical review committee of Utrecht University. Personal data were stored according to the Dutch Law and General Data Protection Regulation as specified at Utrecht University (Utrecht University, 2023). Placenta was collected by midwives, tightly wrapped in aluminum foil, and stored at -80°C without further treatment.

Materials

All chemicals were ordered from Sigma Aldrich, Schnelldorf, Germany. Product numbers and activities or concentrations are provided in Table S1, see online supplementary material. Fluorescently labeled PS spheres of 220 nm (coefficient of variation = 4%, 2.6% aqueous suspension, 4.61×10^{12} particles/mL, 17151-10), 500 nm (coefficient of variation = 3%, 2.5% aqueous suspension, 3.64×10^{11} particles/mL, 17152-10), 1.00 μm (coefficient of variation = 1%, 2.6% aqueous suspension, 3.97×10^{10} particles/mL, 17154-10), and 10.2 μm (coefficient of variation = 8%, 2.7% aqueous suspension, 4.19×10^7 particles/mL, 18140-2) were purchased from Polysciences. They were covalently, internally labeled with Yellow-Green dye, having an excitation maximum at 441 nm and emission maximum at 485 nm.

Figure 1. Experimental setup for evaluating enzymatic digestion protocols and nanoplastic recovery. Placental tissue was digested with enzymes that selectively cut bonds present in tissue and not in plastics. (A) Filter color and residue after filtration were visually assessed to evaluate enzyme effectiveness and determine the best digestion protocol, with a colorless, clean filter indicating a successful digestion and a red, dirty filter indicating an unsuccessful digestion. (B) The procedure was repeated with the most suitable digestion protocol with addition of fluorescent polystyrene (FPS) nanoplastics of 500 nm size. Morphological stability was assessed with confocal fluorescence microscopy (CFM). (C) Recovered particle numbers were counted with CFM to check applicability of this digestion protocol. A total of 45 CFM images were made, 15 of FPS in buffer, 15 of FPS in digestion buffer that underwent the steps of the developed digestion protocol, and 15 of FPS in placental tissue digested with the developed protocol.

Prevention of contamination

During all times, a cotton lab coat was worn, as well as nitrile gloves. Experiments were performed in a laminar flow cabinet. Metal scalpels and scissors were used, that were precleaned with bleach solution, followed by rinsing three times with deionized water and once with ethanol. However, as the aim of this study was to develop a methodology for fluorescent MNP analysis, instead of analyzing environmental MNPs within the sample, prevention of contamination was not of utmost importance since highly fluorescent particles were used.

Sample preparation

The following sample preparation steps were performed on the samples discussed in this paper. For testing the digestion efficiency of placental tissue, only steps 2–5 were performed. Step 1 was later added for testing the stability of FPS particles throughout digestion and for RR determinations. Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of samples that underwent steps 2–5 revealed a background signal, likely originating from the tissue's autofluorescence. This could come from the heme group in red blood cells that may not have been digested fully (Shrirao et al., 2021). Because this autofluorescence interferes with our measurements, as can be seen in Figure S2, see [online supplementary material](#), a phosphate buffered saline (PBS) washing step was added to the digestion protocol as a step prior to the tissue homogenization, to reduce this autofluorescence. This also brought about a change in visible color of the sample after digestion, as can be seen in Figure S3, see [online supplementary material](#). As a result, the autofluorescent signal was reduced to a considerable extent and the FPS particles were well visible. Step 6 was only performed for the samples measured with scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

1. *Washing step to remove autofluorescent signal of blood.* The placenta was thawed at room temperature for 16 hr. Pieces of 10 g were cut and weighed and stored in glass vials in the freezer at -20°C upon further sample processing. Prior to digestion, the placental tissue pieces of 10 g were thawed and cut into smaller pieces with scissors and scalpels. The blood still present in the tissue was washed out by leaving the 1.0 g pieces of tissue in 10 mL PBS for 24 hr in the refrigerator. After this period of time, the blood had diffused out of the tissue, giving the tissue a lighter pink color.
2. *Tissue homogenization.* For testing, the digestion efficiency of eight different enzymes in four different buffers, 32 pieces of (PBS-washed) 1.0 g placental tissue were weighed on a balance and put into separate vials. For RR determinations with the optimal digestion protocol, six pieces of 1.0 g tissue were used, namely three spiked with FPS particles and three without added FPS particles. One milliliter of a buffer was added to each vial. Two microliters of a 25 mg/mL aqueous suspension of 500 nm FPS particles were added. This was deliberately done after the PBS wash, as otherwise the particles would stay in the PBS instead of in the tissue. The tissue pieces were homogenized with a Tissue Tearor rotor/stator type tissue homogenizer with a 32,000 rpm motor, for 1 min on speed 6 out of 10 (19,200 rpm), until a homogeneous slurry was obtained.
3. *Addition of buffer.* In this study, four different buffers were used. They were selected upon their use in other tissue digestion protocols or their use as cell dissociation solutions (Leslie et al., 2022; Mbachu et al., 2021; Wei et al., 2022). The tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris-HCl) buffer was

prepared according to the protocol by Leslie et al. (2022). Approximately 4.85 g tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane was dissolved in 80 mL ultrapure water (UPW). Approximately 0.5 g sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was added to induce cell lysis. pH was adjusted to 8 by adding a few mL of 37% HCl. The pH was measured with pH paper. The solution was complemented with UPW to 100 mL. To all vials, 14 mL of the same buffer that was added prior homogenization was added according to Table 1, so that every vial would contain in total 15 mL of that specific buffer. The SDS was only added to Tris-HCl, as it started to precipitate in other buffers. For lipase and pancreatin (containing lipase), no SDS was added to the Tris-HCl buffer, because SDS is known to inhibit lipase (Borgström & Erlanson, 1973). Pepsin works best at pH 2, so this enzyme was only tested in buffer solutions with added HCl to obtain a pH of 2.

4. *Tissue denaturation.* The homogenized tissue in buffer was denatured in a water bath at 70°C for 1 hr. This high temperature induces protein unfolding, to fasten enzymatic digestion in the next step of this protocol by enhancing the accessibility of the cleavage positions of the protein chains (Park & Marqusee, 2005). After 1 hr, the tissue had turned from red to brown, which indicates that the proteins in the tissue had been denatured (Sen et al., 2014). As shown in Figure S1 in the [online supplementary material](#), higher temperatures induce a change in the FPS spherical morphology when applied for more than 1 hr. Therefore, 70°C for 1 hr was chosen to ensure MNP stability.
5. *Enzyme addition.* Enzyme was added to each sample as indicated in Table 1. The enzyme quantities were deliberately chosen to ensure an excess, guaranteeing that enzyme availability would not limit the reaction. Additionally, ample digestion time was provided, ensuring that neither enzyme concentration nor reaction kinetics served as bottlenecks in the experiment. A 5-mM Ca^{2+} solution was prepared by dissolving 74 mg calcium chloride dihydrate in 100 mL UPW. One milliliter of this solution was added to every sample. Calcium can act as activator for several enzymes such as proteases as it leads to structural stabilization (Eijssink et al., 2011). All samples were vortexed for 5 s and then left in an incubator at 37°C on a RockNRoller shaking plate for 48 hr. After 48 hr, the samples were taken out of the incubator. Samples were stored in the refrigerator until filtration.
6. *Filtration.* Samples made for testing the stability of FPS particles throughout the digestion protocol were vortexed and vacuum filtered over $1.6\ \mu\text{m}$ pore size, 47 mm in diameter glass fiber filters in a tailor-made glass filtration setup. Filters were dried in the incubator at 37°C overnight. The color and cleanliness of the filters indicate the effectiveness of the digestion protocol: less residual tissue on the filter and a lighter color (less red or brown) signify better digestion. The efficiency of enzymatic digestion was evaluated without fluorescent MNPs, by visually inspecting the filter.

Analysis methods

1. *Confocal fluorescence microscopy.* The samples were analyzed with a Nikon Eclipse 90i inverted confocal fluorescence microscope with an A1-DUS spectral detector unit, a Nikon optical microscope attached, and a motorized stage. A DiO laser was used for excitation of the fluorophore in the FPS particles at 488 nm, its emission was detected in the 500–550 nm range. Because placental tissue showed autofluorescence in a broad spectral range, including the narrower

Table 1. Enzymes used and the respective buffers they were tested in.

Enzyme (mixture)	Mass or volume used per sample	Activity specifications	Buffers tested in
Pancreatin	50 mg/mL	4xUSP	Tris-HCl, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
Lipase	4 mg/mL	≥125 units/mg protein	Tris-HCl, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
Proteinase K	1 mg/mL	≥3 units/mg solid	Tris-HCl with SDS, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
Collagenase	4 mg/mL	–	Tris-HCl with SDS, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
Trypsin	2.5 mL/mL	25 g porcine trypsin per liter solution	Tris-HCl with SDS, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
Pepsin	16 mg/mL	≥250 units/mg solid	Tris-HCl with SDS, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
Accutase	4 mL/mL	–	All with pH set to 2
Benzonase nuclease	2 μL/mL	25.3 units/μL	Tris-HCl with SDS, PBS, HBSS, EBSS
			Tris-HCl with SDS, PBS, HBSS, EBSS

Note. Tris-HCl=tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane buffer with hydrogen chloride; PBS=phosphate-buffered saline; HBSS=Hank's balanced salt solution; EBSS=Earle's balanced salt solution; USP=United States pharmacopeia; SDS=sodium dodecyl sulfate.

range in which FPS particles were excited, a DiI laser was used for excitation of the placental tissue to distinguish tissue residue from FPS particles. The DiI laser had an excitation wavelength at 561 nm and its emission was detected at 570–620 nm. The sensitivity (HV) of the lasers was 80 and 60 for DiO and DiI, respectively. The offset was –127 for both lasers and the laser powers were 4.0 for DiO and 2.0 for DiI respectively for 500 nm particles. For 200 nm particles, HV of DiO was set to 150 and DiO laser power to 10. For 1 and 10 μm particles, DiO HV was 60 and DiO laser power was 2. DiI settings were the same for every particle size used, because its signal coming from placental tissue would not change. Images of 4,096 by 4,096 pixels were made, with 1/32 lines/s. A pinhole of 1.2 AU was used. Wavelength resolution was 10 nm and a Nikon 10× magnification air objective was used.

a) *Size-based spot detection method.* With the motorized stage, 3 by 3 images were stitched together automatically with 15% overlap between the 1,750×1,750 μm frames. The NIS elements AR 5.21.03 64-bit software was used for calculating the number of particles in each droplet of the sample. The software identifies brighter pixel regions of a certain spot size separated by darker pixels. The spot size was set to 2 μm for 200 and 500 nm particles, to 3 μm for 1 μm particles and to 10 μm for 10 μm particles. The contrast value for the counting algorithm was set to 800 a.u. This value is a measure for how much background fluorescence was still accepted as “darker pixels.” For the three smaller particle sizes, the chosen spot sizes are larger than the actual particle sizes, because the apparent particle size is usually larger than the actual particle size, because of laser power, pinhole, and Z height influencing the size of the airy disk on the detector. A relatively high laser power and pinhole were used to also visualize particles that were located not exactly at the set Z height (i.e., at the center of the focal plane) within the sample, to ensure that these particles are included in the RR determination. As can be seen in [Figure S4](#), see [online supplementary material](#), varying laser power, pinhole, and Z height can affect the apparent size of the particles. In this work, we are mainly interested in counting particles and showing any possible changes in particle size, making the exact particle size less relevant, as long as the offset between samples is systematic. In [Figure S5](#), see [online supplementary material](#), it can be seen that although the apparent particle sizes are different from the actual particle sizes, the different sizes used in this study

can still be distinguished from each other, and there is little influence of the matrix used on the apparent particle size. Especially when such a large droplet (3 mm in diameter) is imaged with such detail that 500 nm particles can be distinguished, variations in ideal Z height within the droplet appear. Laser power, pinhole, and Z height settings were chosen in such a way that neighboring particles could still be separated without losing signal in other regions of the droplet. Histograms and boxplots were made of the sizes of all particles imaged in a droplet, as calculated with this method.

b) *Intensity-based spot detection method.* To show the stability in particle size throughout the digestion protocol, particle size distributions (PSDs) were made with the NIS Elements AR 5.21.03 64-bit software. The software can count particles by selecting all pixels with a fluorescence intensity in a certain range. All pixels in the collected images had an intensity at a scale from 0 to 8,190, with 0 meaning no signal, and 8,190 meaning the maximum fluorescence intensity. Because the FPS particles have fluorescence intensity, all pixels were selected with an intensity in the range 3,000–8,190 in order to select all FPS particles. To ensure that large agglomerates of several FPS particles are not counted as one large particle, thereby altering the PSD, the maximum spot size was set to 6 μm for 500 nm particles. To achieve the same for other particle sizes, the maximum spot size for 200 nm particles was set to 3 μm, for 1 μm particles, it was set to 10 μm, and for 10 μm particles, it was set to 20 μm. These maximum spot sizes are again larger than the actual particle sizes of single particles, but the spot size was based on the larger apparent particle size in CFM. Every region of interest of a few neighboring selected pixels was now seen as a particle, and the equivalent diameter was calculated by the software. Because some of the tissue residue on the edges of the droplets had a similar intensity to that of the FPS particles, this intensity range was chosen to be more conservative rather than to allow also tissue residue to be counted falsely as particles. Therefore, the RR with this intensity-based method is slightly lower. Because CFM results show that there is little variety between samples of the same type, these calculations were only performed on the first droplet of each triplicate sample. The loss of RR between both methods is defined as the RR of the size-based spot detection method minus the RR of the intensity-based spot detection used for PSD calculations.

2. *Scanning electron microscopy.* Scanning electron microscopy was measured on a Helios Nanolab G3 ThermoFisher Scientific microscope, using a beam current of 25 pA and an acceleration voltage of 2 kV. Two microliters of each sample type (particles in buffer, particles that underwent the digestion steps excluding tissue, and particles that underwent the digestion steps including tissue), were added to 5 mL of ultrapure water. This was vacuum filtered over 375 nm pore size alumina (Al₂O₃) filters of 3.6 mm in diameter. The filters had been precleaned in a calcination oven with a ramp of 10 °C/min to 600 °C, staying there for 2 hr. After the filtration, the filter was flushed with 5 mL water, to decrease the chances of pore blocking during drying of the sample, as residual tissue could crystallize upon drying and thereby blocking the filter pores. By flushing the filter, the residual tissue was diluted, and crystallization took place to a lesser extent. Then, the filters were sputter-coated with a platinum coating of 7 nm using a sputter coater (Cressington 208HR) equipped with a thickness controller (Cressington MTM20), and measured with SEM.
3. *Dynamic light scattering.* Dynamic light scattering (DLS) was measured on a ZetaSizer Nano S Malvern Instruments at a fixed scattering angle of 173°. Four hundred microliters of each sample were pipetted into a microcuvette. Dynamic light scattering was measured at 20 °C in triplicates.

Quality assurance and quality control

1. *Digestion of placental tissue.* The filters and the liquids after digestion were inspected visually after the 48-hr incubation period to assess the ease of filtration and the residue on the filters after filtration. For the liquids, the viscosity, color, and amount of solid left-over material were assessed. A red color, viscous substance, or solid left-overs indicate the presence of undigested blood and/or tissue, hence an unsuccessful digestion, whereas a clear, less viscous liquid without solids indicates the successful breakdown of tissue. For the filters, the color and amount of solid material were assessed. Here, again a red color and/or solid pieces on the filter indicate the presence of blood or tissue, thus an unsuccessful digestion, whereas a clear, colorless filter indicates a successful digestion.
2. *Stability of FPS particles against the digestion protocol.* The morphological stability of FPS particles against the conditions used in the digestion protocols was tested with CFM. Two microliters of a 25 mg/mL (50 µg) aqueous suspension of 500 nm FPS particles were added to 15 mL of buffer solution. The solution was then subjected to each condition in the digestion protocol separately: homogenization, denaturation, digestion, and to all three steps combined. The conditions for these samples were as follows:
 - Blank: FPS particles in buffer left in the refrigerator.
 - Homogenization: FPS particles in buffer were “homogenized” for 1 min on speed 6 out of 10 (19,200 rpm).
 - Denaturation: FPS particles in buffer were “denatured” for 1 hr at 70 °C.
 - Digestion: FPS particles in 15 mL buffer were “digested” with the corresponding amount of enzyme, given in Table 1, 48 hr at 37 °C.
 - Combination of these three steps: FPS particles were first “homogenized,” then “denatured” and then “digested” with enzyme.

3. *RR determination.* For determination of the RR, no filtration step was performed on the samples after digestion. Instead, the sample was vortexed and 1.0 µL of the sample was pipetted with a 0.2–1.0 µL micropipette onto a 170 ± 5 µm thick microscopy glass slide. This analyte volume was half the size of the volume the sample was originally spiked with, because a larger analyte volume would increase the area of the sample droplet and therefore increase the measurement time. The sample was air dried. The following sample types were made:
 - Buffer control (B): FPS particles in digestion buffer, stored in the refrigerator. No digestion steps were performed on this sample.
 - Whole Protocol (WP): FPS particles in digestion buffer, subjected to all steps in the digestion protocol, i.e., homogenization, denaturation, and enzymatic digestion.
 - Tissue (T): FPS particles in digestion buffer with added placental tissue, subjected to all steps in the digestion protocol, i.e., homogenization, denaturation, and enzymatic digestion.
 - Unspiked B: Digestion buffer without added FPS, stored in the refrigerator. No digestion steps were performed on this sample.
 - Unspiked WP: digestion buffer without added FPS, subjected to all steps in the digestion protocol, i.e., homogenization, denaturation, and enzymatic digestion.
 - Unspiked T: digestion buffer with added placental tissue without added FPS, subjected to all steps in the digestion protocol, i.e., homogenization, denaturation, and enzymatic digestion.

Samples were made in triplicates, meaning three pieces of 1.0 g tissue were digested separately. From every triplicate, five 1.0 µL droplets were pipetted to also make five technical replicates for analysis. Every droplet was imaged entirely with CFM using a stitching approach of nine individual images of 1,750 × 1,750 µm with 15% overlap, creating a 4,780 × 4,780 µm image. All particles in each droplet were counted with the NIS elements AR 5.21.03 64-bit software Nikon, 2025 (Nikon, 2025). The number of particles in the 2 µL stock solution was not counted, as this large number of particles would give a saturated image in which no particles could be distinguished. A comparison could be made between the number of particles counted in each droplet and the expected number based on the droplet's volume and the FPS stock concentration. The comparison in percentages is called the RR, and is calculated in the following way:

$$\text{Recovery rate (\%)} = \frac{\# \text{ of particles counted on CFM image}}{\left(\frac{\# \text{ particles in } 2 \mu\text{L FPS stock solution}}{\text{total volume of sample}} * \text{volume of CFM droplet} \right)} * 100\%$$

Results and discussion

Digestion of placental tissue

Pictures of all filters are shown in Figure 2. Green check marks indicate a successful digestion, orange bars indicate only partial digestion, and red crosses indicate an unsuccessful digestion.

Based on this assessment, proteinase K in Tris–HCl buffer and trypsin in Tris–HCl buffer were identified as most optimal enzyme–buffer combinations for the digestion of human

Figure 2. Pictures of 1.6 μm pore size, 47 mm in diameter glass fiber filters after filtration of digested tissue. The color and cleanliness of the filters are an indication of how well the digestion protocol worked. Green checks indicate a successful digestion, orange bars indicate a partial digestion, and red crosses indicate an unsuccessful digestion. Note. Tris-HCl=tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane buffer with hydrogen chloride; PBS=phosphate-buffered saline; HBSS=Hank's balanced salt solution; EBSS=Earle's balanced salt solution; SDS=sodium dodecyl sulfate.

placental tissue, as those filters exhibited almost no color change and contained no visible solids. Because placental tissue contains 48 g of proteins per placenta, compared to only 4 g of fat, it makes sense that proteases such as proteinase K and trypsin are successful enzymes to digest placental tissue (Johnson et al., 2018). We chose proteinase K over trypsin because it is a powdered enzyme, making it easier to handle. Trypsin, a liquid which requires frozen storage, and repeated freeze-thaw cycles might reduce its activity. The Tris-HCl buffer may be the optimal buffer because it contains SDS, which promotes cell lysis by forming micelles that disrupt the cell membrane (Leslie et al., 2022).

Benzonase nuclease breaks down DNA and RNA thus it could be a useful step after trypsin or proteinase K digestion. In our study, a multi-enzyme digestion with trypsin, proteinase K, and benzonase nuclease combined was also explored, as can be seen in Figure S6, see [online supplementary material](#), but based on the visual inspection of the filters, the digestion was not improved. Because extra steps could lead to particle loss, we decided not to include it in our digestion protocol.

Stability of FPS throughout digestions

With CFM, it was analyzed whether 500 nm FPS spheres stayed "intact" during the different steps of the digestion protocol. Intact here means that particles do not agglomerate to such an extent that the individual particles cannot be distinguished anymore, that their size, shape, and surface do not change as far as can be seen with CFM, and dye leaching is minimal. In Figure 3A–E, CFM images are shown of FPS in samples collected at different steps of the protocol. These images are zoom-ins from images collected of the entire droplets of 1.0 μL of each sample.

Below the CFM images, histograms of the size distribution of particles, as well as boxplots of the PSD of all the particles in the entire imaged droplet can be seen. In the CFM images and PSD boxplots, no significant agglomeration or particle degradation was observed as, for example, clearly visible for protocols in

which elevated temperatures are used for a longer time (see [online supplementary material](#); Figure S1).

Dye leaching cannot be completely ruled out, but as can be seen in the CFM images, it is not significant enough to obscure or prevent the clear detection of individual particles. Figure 3A and E show somewhat broader PSDs, as can be seen both in the images and in the PSD graphs. This broader size distribution may indicate some degree of clustering, but the difference is minimal and does not hamper detection of single particles.

As discussed before, CFM is not an ideal technique for size determination because of varying apparent particle sizes for different laser powers, pinhole size, and Z height. To exclude size changes caused by the digestion protocol, these samples were also analyzed with SEM and DLS. In Figure 3F–H, the SEM results can be seen of particles in the buffer control (sample B, Figure 3F), particles subjected to the whole digestion protocol (sample WP, Figure 3G), and particles subjected to the digestion protocol with added tissue (sample T, Figure 3H). It can be observed that particles have similar size and shape in all three sample types. The DLS results, shown in Table S5, see [online supplementary material](#), show that the Z-Average is not significantly changed by the denaturation step ("500 nm FPS, denatured," of which the CFM image is shown in Figure 3C) or by the enzyme addition step ("500 nm FPS, enzyme added," CFM image shown in Figure 3D) when compared to "500 nm FPS in buffer (B)," CFM shown in Figure 3A. However, a change in Z-Average is observed when the particles are homogenized ("500 nm FPS, homogenized," CFM image shown in Figure 3B). The combination of these steps, "500 nm FPS in Whole Protocol, without tissue (WP)," CFM image shown in Figure 3E, also shows an increased Z-Average, as do "500 nm FPS in whole protocol, with Tissue (T)" and "Unspiked tissue (no FPS particles)." This implies that digested tissue still contains some compounds that are not fully digested into short, solvable amino acid chains and therefore increase the size distribution. As CFM images still show that the

Figure 3. Confocal fluorescence microscopy images, histograms, and particle size distribution (PSD) boxplots of fluorescent polystyrene (FPS) in buffer without any steps performed (A), throughout tissue homogenization with the Tissue Tearer (B), after tissue denaturation (C), after proteinase K digestion (D), and (B–D) combined, leading to the complete digestion protocol (E). The laser settings and intensity profiles are the same for every image shown here. (F–H) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of 500 nm FPS in Tris–HCl buffer (F), 500 nm FPS that underwent the steps of the digestion protocol without tissue included (G), and 500 nm FPS that underwent the steps of the digestion protocol with tissue included with white circles indicating the FPS particles (H). With tissue included, the FPS particles became more difficult to find with SEM.

appearance and PSD of FPS particles are unchanged during homogenization, this shows that the FPS spheres are stable under the conditions used in the digestion protocol.

Initially, enzymes were inactivated to stop the reactions by heating the samples in a water bath to 90°C for 10 min. As demonstrated in Figure S7c, see [online supplementary material](#), this step on its own seemed not to affect the stability of FPS. Only changes in morphology were observed for heat treatments for longer times, as was shown in Figure S1b, see [online supplementary material](#), but Figure S7a, see [online supplementary material](#), shows that the inactivation of enzymes seemed to change the

chemical environment of the sample and thereby the clustering behavior of the FPS particles.

RR determination

Figure 4A–C shows selected images of entire 1.0 μL droplets of three different sample types measured with CFM, namely sample type B, shown in Figure 4A, sample type WP, shown in Figure 4B, and sample type T, shown in Figure 4C. Zoom-ins of both the middle and edge of the pipetted droplets of these three sample types show that also with the tissue sample (C), particles can clearly be distinguished from the background fluorescent signal

Figure 4. Confocal fluorescence microscopy images of entire droplets of fluorescent polystyrene (FPS) particles in sample type B (A), sample type whole protocol (WP), (B), and sample type tissue (T), (C), including zoom-ins of the aforementioned samples in two different regions: edge (light pink) and middle (dark pink), and particle size distributions (PSDs) of the FPS particles in the whole droplet of every triplicate of every sample type. Y axis shows the percentage of the number of particles within a certain size range in μm , which are on the X axis.

Table 2. Relative recovery rates (%) of the three sample types containing 500 nm fluorescent polystyrene particles, normalized to the buffer control.

Sample type (particles in)	Recovery rate (%; n = 15) compared to buffer sample
Buffer (Sample B)	100 ± 8
Whole protocol without tissue (Sample WP)	92 ± 4
Whole protocol with tissue (Sample T)	148 ± 0

of the tissue. All measured images can also be found in Figures S8–S10, see [online supplementary material](#). In Figure S11, see [online supplementary material](#), images are shown of non-spiked samples.

To assess the RR for our digestion and analytical protocol, the average RR from five droplets of three triplicates (n = 15) of the particles in the buffer sample (Sample B, Figure 4A) was used as a reference, setting it to 100%. The RR for the WP and T samples was reported as relative to sample B, as can be seen in Table 2. The RR based on the manufacturer's particle concentrations revealed that 79% ± 6 of the expected FPS particles were recovered in the buffer solution, suggesting 21% loss of particles to buffer solution only. Seventy-nine percent recovery was thus set as analytical RR. As the SD is only 6, a consistently lower number of particles is being found back with this analysis technique. The exact particle numbers counted by the CFM software in each droplet can also be found in Table S3, see [online supplementary material](#).

When the particles were subjected to the full digestion protocol without tissue (Sample WP, Figure 4B), 92% of the particles were retained. We therefore conclude that the particles remained stable, both in terms of morphology and number throughout the described digestion protocol.

Surprisingly, including tissue (Sample T, Figure 4C) to the digestion procedure led to a higher particle count by the CFM software, as compared to the whole digestion procedure without tissue. It is unlikely this was due to increased background levels in the CFM images since a nonspiked tissue (blank) showed only a 0.5% RR (see [online supplementary material](#); Table S3). Nevertheless, for spiked samples, it can be expected that some dye leaching might occur during the digestion protocol. The dye, which is not present in the unspiked sample, can then bind to organic residue present from the tissue. This “unintentional staining” of tissue residue with leached dye leads to more spots being falsely recognized as particles if the residue contains features that have a similar size as the FPS. If this is the case, distinguishing “dyed” organic residue and FPS of the same size will be very difficult when staining environmental samples to selectively stain MNPs. This dye leaching and unintentional staining forms one of the limitations of this MNP analysis method using fluorescence, together with the absence of fluorescent MNPs in environmental samples and the dependence on the success of staining environmental samples. Even though these limitations may be difficult to overcome in environmental samples, this method still provides a robust and fast way of analyzing the stability and RR of fluorescent model MNPs, which is an important step in the validation of any digestion protocol.

Explaining increased RR for samples containing tissue

To see whether stained tissue residue has a different size than the FPS particles, PSDs were established and inspected. The

Table 3. Relative recovery rates (RRs) for different particle sizes, compared to the buffer samples which are set to 100%.

Sample type	Relative RR (n = 3) 200 nm particles	Relative RR (n = 15) 500 nm particles	Relative RR (n = 3) 1 μm particles	Relative RR (n = 3) 10 μm particles
Buffer (B)	100% ± 8	100 ± 8	100% ± 9	100% ± 12
Whole protocol without tissue (WP)	78% ± 6	92 ± 4	58% ± 9	94% ± 19
Whole protocol with tissue (T)	98% ± 6	148 ± 0	147% ± 8	81% ± 8

histogram and size distribution of all particles in all droplets of each triplicate and of each of the three sample types (B, WP, T) were determined and are shown in Figure 4 under the CFM images of the corresponding sample types (A–C). The counted number of particles, the average particle size, and its SD are also shown in the PSD graph legends. All PSDs shown in Figure 4 have the highest number of particles within the range 1.0–1.5 μm. There are only a few outliers with higher or lower particle size for the samples containing tissue, meaning there are few to no spots that were falsely counted as particles based on their size. There is little variation between the triplicates of each sample type (B: 1.38 ± 0.49 μm, WP: 1.51 ± 0.56 μm, T: 1.29 ± 0.32 μm). WP has a larger SD than B, whereas T has a smaller SD than B, as is also reflected in the RRs shown in Table S2 of the [online supplementary material](#). This large variety in particle sizes for WP and small variety for T can also be seen qualitatively in the microscopy images 4(A–C) and implies that any spots that may be falsely counted as particles indeed have a similar size as actual particles.

As shown in Table S4 and Figure S12, see [online supplementary material](#), where we evaluated the mean size, mean circularity, and mean intensity of all identified objects, we could not detect any objects that differed significantly from the expected properties of FPS particles. This concludes that the higher RR for T samples can at this stage only be explained by spots that are still falsely counted as particles but in the data collected by the CFM do not appear different from actual particles, because they have a similar size, shape, and intensity, because they are dyed by some dye leaching from the fluorescent dye from the particles.

Digestion protocol applied to different particle sizes

To test whether there is a specific size range of tissue residue that is stained by this digestion protocol, the protocol was repeated with different particle sizes, namely 200 nm, 1 μm, and 10 μm particles. If dye leaching occurs, and the dye then binds to organic residue which has a certain size range in the same size range as the 500 nm FPS particles, it is possible that this phenomenon is enhanced for 500 nm particles, but less prominent for other particle sizes. Potentially, false positives could then be avoided. The RRs obtained using CFM are reported in Table 3 and their PSDs are shown in Figure 5. Since the same mass concentrations were used for each particle size, the particle numbers vary per test. As can be seen, 200 nm and 10 μm particles have a similar PSD for each sample type (B, WP, and T), while 1 μm particles show the same trend as 500 nm particles, namely a broader PSD for the WP sample and a narrower PSD for the T sample. In Table S2, see [online supplementary material](#), the RR based on the nominal concentrations of the stock solution as provided by the manufacturer is shown. However, nominal concentrations can

Figure 5. Particle size distributions of the three sample types of three different particle sizes, namely 200 nm, 1 μm, and 10 μm.

change as a function of shelf life, which can be seen for the 200 nm, 1 μm, and 10 μm particles which were purchased much earlier than the 500 nm particles. Therefore, we decided to rely on normalized concentrations based on the buffer solution, as

shown in Table 3. This further emphasizes the necessity of a standardized protocol and analysis method, as these lower RRs could significantly impact our data interpretation.

As can be seen in Table 3, the RR of the sample digested without tissue (WP) is always below 100%, which is expected as every added step in a procedure comes with a possible loss of particles. The relative RR of the WP sample of the 1 μm particles is surprisingly low. At this stage, we do not know why this was the case. WP samples that have high RR tend to exhibit greater SDs, suggesting that agglomeration or particle loss may occur. In contrast, tissue samples (T) contain more organic matter, which could act as a dispersion agent, potentially reducing the likelihood of agglomeration or loss. There is a larger and comparably higher RR for the tissue samples in which 500 nm and 1 μm particles are used, which, if our hypothesis is correct, shows that the digested tissue results in left-over particulate material of around this (500 nm–1 μm) size. This hypothesis is strengthened by the DLS results in Table S5, see online supplementary material, showing that any step containing tissue homogenization and thus introducing tissue residue as “contamination” into the sample, leads to 500–1,000 nm Z-Average values. It is thus likely that tissue residue absorbs the leached-out dye, thereby appearing as “stained particles” in this size range. Table S5, see online supplementary material, also shows that nonspiked tissue has a “particle” size of 603 nm ± 142. This is an important validation and hence placental model studies using FPS should rather use particle sizes below 500 nm or above 1,000 nm in diameter to avoid such false positives.

Conclusion

In this study, an optimized digestion protocol was designed for the analysis of MNPs in ex vivo human placental cells priorly isolated from human placental tissue, as schematically highlighted in Figure 6. Digestion with proteinase K in Tris–HCl buffer with pH 8 and added SDS was found to be most optimal. Intentionally added FPS particles were morphologically stable throughout this digestion, as was shown with CFM and SEM. Recovery rates of 98% ± 6 for 200 nm FPS particles, 148% ± 8 for 500 nm FPS particles, 147% ± 8 for 1 μm FPS particles, and 81% ± 8 for 10 μm FPS particles were found after digestion of 1.0 g placental tissue with the preferred digestion protocol, normalized to a 100% RR for particles in buffer. The observed effect of an increased RR found for 500 nm and 1 μm particles in tissue was investigated, and evidence is provided suggesting fluorescent dye leaching during digestion. The dye can then bind to “particulate” (i.e., fairly spherical) tissue residue of a similar size range resulting in objects with similar fluorescence intensity, which is a phenomenon worth taking into consideration while working with spiked digested tissue. The 200 nm particles are below the nominal resolution of CFM, which makes detection of fluorescent particles of this size increasingly hard. The digestion protocol has proven to work well for a broad size range (200 nm to 10 μm) of both MNP PS particles. The presented work here provides ways for a more accurate risk analysis of MNPs, or any particulate matter, in placentas, providing the tools to properly process complex organic matrices. The very efficient cell digestion obtained, and the subsequent preparation technique of the cell fraction can significantly facilitate subsequent, specific MNP analysis using sensitive techniques. Especially for Raman spectroscopy, highly relevant interferences by fluorescence were minimized and possible sources of interference were addressed and localized. As a next step, “environmental” MNP particles

Figure 6. Optimized digestion protocol used in this study to digest human placental tissue for micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) characterization with (spectro-)microscopic techniques. Note. PBS=phosphate-buffered saline; Tris-HCl=tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane with hydrogen chloride; SDS=sodium dodecyl sulfate; FPS=fluorescent polystyrene particles; CFM=confocal fluorescence microscopy.

could be selectively fluorescently stained after matrix digestion, allowing for accurate analysis using the developed digestion methodology.

Supplementary material

Supplementary material is available online at *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*.

Author contributions

Laura Miranda Zoutendijk (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing), Zenzi Matla (Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing—review & editing), Hanna Marta Dusza (Writing—review & editing), Barbara M Scholz-Böttcher (Writing—review & editing), Bert Marc Weckhuysen (Writing—review & editing), Laurens Dirk Bernardus Mandemaker (Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing—review & editing), and Florian Meirer (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing—review & editing)

Funding

This research was supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under AURORA grant agreement number 964827.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank S. Hadidimasouleh (Utrecht University, UU) for preparing the samples for SEM measurements, A. Duijndam (UU) for measuring SEM, L. van Dalen (UU) for measuring CFM on the 200 nm FPS particles at elevated temperatures, shown in Figure 1B and in Figure S1, see online supplementary material, and B. Juffer (UU) for helping with the development of the PBS washing step added to the digestion protocol.

Data availability

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary information. More data that support the findings of this study are available on Yoda upon request from the corresponding author.

References

- Alexander, J., Barregård, L., Bignami, M., Ceccatelli, S., Cottrill, B., Dinovi, M., Edler, L., Grasl-Kraupp, B., Hogstrand, C., Hoogenboom, L., Knutsen, H. K., Nebbia, C. S., Oswald, I., Petersen, A., Rogiers, V. M., Rose, M., Roudot, A., Schwerdtle, T., Vleminckx, C., & Wallace, H. (2016). Presence of microplastics and nanoplastics in food, with particular focus on seafood. *EFSA Journal*, 14, e04501. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2016.4501>

- Alimi, O. S., Farmer Budarz, J., Hernandez, L. M., & Tufenkji, N. (2018). Microplastics and nanoplastics in aquatic environments: Aggregation, deposition, and enhanced contaminant transport. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 52, 1704–1724. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b05559>
- Bongaerts, E., Nawrot, T. S., Van Pee, T., Ameloot, M., & Bové, H. (2020). Translocation of (ultra)fine particles and nanoparticles across the placenta; A systematic review on the evidence of in vitro, ex vivo, and in vivo studies. *Particle and Fibre Toxicology*, 17, 56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12989-020-00386-8>
- Borgström, B., & Erlanson, C. (1973). Pancreatic lipase and co-lipase. *European Journal of Biochemistry*, 37, 60–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1432-1033.1973.tb02957.x>
- Brits, M., van Velzen, M. J. M., Sefiloglu, F. Ö., Scibetta, L., Groenewoud, Q., Garcia-Vallejo, J. J., Vethaak, A. D., Brandsma, S. H., & Lamoree, M. H. (2024). Quantitation of micro and nanoplastics in human blood by pyrolysis-gas chromatography–mass spectrometry. *Microplastics and Nanoplastics*, 4, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43591-024-00090-w>
- Catarino, A. I., Thompson, R., Sanderson, W., & Henry, T. B. (2017). Development and optimization of a standard method for extraction of microplastics in mussels by enzyme digestion of soft tissues. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 36, 947–951. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc3608>
- Christopher, E. A., Christopher-de Vries, Y., Devadoss, A., Mandemaker, L. D. B., van Boxel, J., Copsey, H. M., Dusza, H. M., Legler, J., Meirer, F., Muncke, J., Nawrot, T. S., Saenen, N. D., Scholz-Böttcher, B. M., Tran, L., Weckhuysen, B. M., Zou, R., Zimmermann, L., Galea, K. S., Vermeulen, R., & Boyles, M. S. P. (2024). Impacts of micro- and nanoplastics on early-life health: A roadmap towards risk assessment. *Microplastics and Nanoplastics*, 4, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43591-024-00089-3>
- Correia, M., & Loeschner, K. (2018). Detection of nanoplastics in food by asymmetric flow field-flow fractionation coupled to multi-angle light scattering: Possibilities, challenges and analytical limitations. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 410, 5603–5615. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-018-0919-8>
- Courteney-Jones, W., Quinn, B., Murphy, F., Gary, S. F., & Narayanaswamy, B. E. (2017). Optimisation of enzymatic digestion and validation of specimen preservation methods for the analysis of ingested microplastics. *Analytical Methods*, 9, 1437–1445. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6AY02343F>
- Dusza, H. M., Katrukha, E. A., Nijmeijer, S. M., Akhmanova, A., Vethaak, A. D., Walker, D. I., & Legler, J. (2022). Uptake, transport, and toxicity of pristine and weathered micro- and nanoplastics in human placenta cells. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 130, 97006. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP10873>
- Eijsink, V. G. H., Matthews, B. W., & Vriend, G. (2011). The role of calcium ions in the stability and instability of a thermolysin-like protease. *Protein Science: A Publication of the Protein Society*, 20, 1346–1355. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.670>
- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J. R., & Law, K. L. (2017). Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Science Advances*, 3, e1700782. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1700782>
- Gigault, J., ter Halle, A., Baudrimont, M., Pascal, P. Y., Gauffre, F., Phi, T. L., Hadri, H. El, Grassl, B., & Reynaud, S. (2018). Current opinion: What is a nanoplastic? *Environmental Pollution*, 235, 1030–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.01.024>
- Grafmueller, S., Manser, P., Diener, L., Maurizi, L., Diener, P. A., Hofmann, H., Jochum, W., Krug, H. F., Buerki-Thurnherr, T., von Mandach, U., & Wick, P. (2015). Transfer studies of polystyrene nanoparticles in the ex vivo human placenta perfusion model: Key sources of artifacts. *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials*, 16, 044602. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1468-6996/16/4/044602>
- Gruber, M. M., Hirschmugl, B., Berger, N., Holter, M., Radulović, S., Leitinger, G., Liesinger, L., Berghold, A., Roblegg, E., Birner-Gruenberger, R., Bjelic-Radisic, V., & Wadsack, C. (2020). Plasma proteins facilitates placental transfer of polystyrene particles. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 18, 128. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-020-00676-5>
- Hernandez, L. M., Xu, E. G., Larsson, H. C. E., Tahara, R., Maisuria, V. B., & Tufenkji, N. (2019). Plastic teabags release billions of microparticles and nanoparticles into tea. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 53, 12300–12310. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b02540>
- Hildebrandt, L., Nack, F. L., Zimmermann, T., & Pröfrock, D. (2021). Microplastics as a Trojan horse for trace metals. *Journal of Hazardous Materials Letters*, 2, 100035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazl.2021.100035>
- Horton, A. A., Walton, A., Spurgeon, D. J., Lahive, E., & Svendsen, C. (2017). Microplastics in freshwater and terrestrial environments: Evaluating the current understanding to identify the knowledge gaps and future research priorities. *Science of the Total Environment*, 586, 127–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.01.190>
- Hurley, R. R., Lusher, A. L., Olsen, M., & Nizzetto, L. (2018). Validation of a method for extracting microplastics from complex, organic-rich, environmental matrices. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 52, 7409–7417. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b01517>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2020). *Plastics—environmental aspects—state of knowledge and methodologies*. International Organization for Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:tr:21960:ed-1:v1:en>
- Johnson, S. K., Pastuschek, J., Rödel, J., Markert, U. R., & Groten, T. (2018). Placenta—Worth trying? Human maternal placentophagia: Possible benefit and potential risks. *Geburtshilfe Und Frauenheilkunde*, 78, 846–852. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-0674-6275>
- Karami, A., Golieskardi, A., Choo, C. K., Romano, N., Ho, Y. B., & Salamatinia, B. (2017). A high-performance protocol for extraction of microplastics in fish. *Science of the Total Environment*, 578, 485–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.213>
- Karlsson, T. M., Vethaak, A. D., Almroth, B. C., Ariese, F., van Velzen, M., Hassellöv, M., & Leslie, H. A. (2017). Screening for microplastics in sediment, water, marine invertebrates and fish: Method development and microplastic accumulation. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 122, 403–408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.06.081>
- Koelmans, A. A., Besseling, E., & Shim, W. J. (2015). Nanoplastics in the aquatic environment. Critical review. In M. Bergmann, L. Gutow, & M. Klages (Eds.), *Marine anthropogenic litter* (pp. 325–340). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16510-3_12
- Leslie, H. A., van Velzen, M. J. M., Brandsma, S. H., Vethaak, A. D., Garcia-Vallejo, J. J., & Lamoree, M. H. (2022). Discovery and quantification of plastic particle pollution in human blood. *Environment International*, 163, 107199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107199>
- Liebezeit, G., & Liebezeit, E. (2014). Synthetic particles as contaminants in German beers. *Food Additives & Contaminants. Part A, Chemistry, Analysis, Control, Exposure & Risk Assessment*, 31, 1574–1578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2014.945099>
- Löder, M. G. J., Imhof, H. K., Ladehoff, M., Löscher, L. A., Lorenz, C., Mintenig, S., Piehl, S., Primpke, S., Schrank, I., Laforsch, C., & Gerdts, G. (2017). Enzymatic purification of microplastics in

- environmental samples. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 51, 14283–14292. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b03055>
- Malmqvist, E., Jakobsson, K., Tinnerberg, H., Rignell-Hydbom, A., & Rylander, L. (2013). Gestational diabetes and preeclampsia in association with air pollution at levels below current air quality guidelines. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 121, 488–493. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1205736>
- Mandemaker, L. D. B., & Meirer, F. (2023). Spectro-microscopic techniques for studying nanoplastics in the environment and in organisms. *Angewandte Chemie*, 62, e202210494. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202210494>
- Mbachu, O., Jenkins, G., Pratt, C., & Kaparaju, P. (2021). Enzymatic purification of microplastics in soil. *MethodsX*, 8, 101254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2021.101254>
- Nikon. (2025). NIS-Elements Viewer. Nikon. https://www.microscope.healthcare.nikon.com/en_EU/products/software/nis-elements/software-resources
- Park, C., & Marqusee, S. (2005). Pulse proteolysis: A simple method for quantitative determination of protein stability and ligand binding. *Nature Methods*, 2, 207–212. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth740>
- Ragusa, A., Matta, M., Cristiano, L., Matassa, R., Battaglione, E., Svelato, A., De Luca, C., D'Avino, S., Gulotta, A., Rongioletti, M. C. A., Catalano, P., Santacroce, C., Notarstefano, V., Carnevali, O., Giorgini, E., Vizza, E., Familiari, G., & Nottola, S. A. (2022a). Deeply in plasticenta: Presence of microplastics in the intracellular compartment of human placentas. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19, 11593. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191811593>
- Ragusa, A., Notarstefano, V., Svelato, A., Belloni, A., Gioacchini, G., Blondeel, C., Zucchelli, E., De Luca, C., D'Avino, S., Gulotta, A., Carnevali, O., & Giorgini, E. (2022b). Raman microspectroscopy detection and characterisation of microplastics in human breastmilk. *Polymers*, 14, 2700. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14132700>
- Ragusa, A., Svelato, A., Santacroce, C., Catalano, P., Notarstefano, V., Carnevali, O., Papa, F., Rongioletti, M. C. A., Baiocco, F., Draghi, S., D'Amore, E., Rinaldo, D., Matta, M., & Giorgini, E. (2021). Plasticenta: First evidence of microplastics in human placenta. *Environment International*, 146, 106274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106274>
- Rauert, C., Pan, Y., Okoffo, E. D., O'Brien, J. W., & Thomas, K. V. (2022). Extraction and Pyrolysis-GC-MS analysis of polyethylene in samples with medium to high lipid content. *Journal of Environmental Exposure Assessment*, 1, 13. <https://dx.doi.org/10.20517/jeea.2022.04>
- Rios Mendoza, L. M., Karapanagioti, H., & Álvarez, N. R. (2018). Micro (nanoplastics) in the marine environment: Current knowledge and gaps. *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health*, 1, 47–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.COESH.2017.11.004>
- Sen, A. R., Naveena, B. M., Muthukumar, M., & Vaithyanathan, S. (2014). Colour, myoglobin denaturation and storage stability of raw and cooked mutton chops at different end point cooking temperature. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 51, 970–975. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-011-0557-z>
- Shao, K., Zou, R., Zhang, Z., Mandemaker, L. D. B., Timbie, S., Smith, R. D., Durkin, A. M., Dusza, H. M., Meirer, F., Weckhuysen, B. M., Alderete, T. L., Vermeulen, R., & Walker, D. I. (2025). Advancements in assays for micro- and nanoplastic detection: Paving the way for biomonitoring and exposomics studies. *Annual Review of Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 65, 567–585. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pharmtox-030424-112828>
- Shrirao, A. B., Schloss, R. S., Fritz, Z., Shrirao, M. V., Rosen, R., & Yarmush, M. L. (2021). Autofluorescence of blood and its application in biomedical and clinical research. *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 118, 4550–4576. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.27933>
- Stock, V., Fahrenson, C., Thuenemann, A., Dönmez, M. H., Voss, L., Böhmert, L., Braeuning, A., Lampen, A., & Sieg, H. (2020). Impact of artificial digestion on the sizes and shapes of microplastic particles. *Food and Chemical Toxicology: An International Journal Published for the British Industrial Biological Research Association*, 135, 111010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2019.111010>
- Su, X., Zhao, Y., Yang, Y., & Hua, J. (2020). Correlation between exposure to fine particulate matter and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in Shanghai, China. *Environmental Health*, 19, 101. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-020-00655-1>
- Ter Halle, A., Jeanneau, L., Martignac, M., Jardé, E., Pedrono, B., Brach, L., & Gigault, J. (2017). Nanoplastic in the North Atlantic subtropical gyre. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 51, 13689–13697. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b03667>
- Thiele, C. J., Hudson, M. D., & Russell, A. E. (2019). Evaluation of existing methods to extract microplastics from bivalve tissue: Adapted KOH digestion protocol improves filtration at single-digit pore size. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 142, 384–393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.03.003>
- Utrecht University. (2023). Privacy statement participants scientific research. Utrecht University. <https://www.uu.nl/en/organisatie/practical-matters/privacy/privacy-statements-utrecht-university/privacy-statement-participants-scientific-research>
- von Friesen, L. W., Granberg, M. E., Hassellöv, M., Gabrielsen, G. W., & Magnusson, K. (2019). An efficient and gentle enzymatic digestion protocol for the extraction of microplastics from bivalve tissue. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 142, 129–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.03.016>
- Walczak, A. P., Kramer, E., Hendriksen, P. J. M., Tromp, P., Helsen, J. P. F. G., van der Zande, M., Rietjens, I. M. C. M., & Bouwmester, H. (2015). Translocation of differently sized and charged polystyrene nanoparticles in vitro intestinal cell models of increasing complexity. *Nanotoxicology*, 9, 453–461. <https://doi.org/10.3109/17435390.2014.944599>
- Wei, X.-F., Capezza, A. J., Cui, Y., Li, L., Hakonen, A., Liu, B., & Hedenqvist, M. S. (2022). Millions of microplastics released from a biodegradable polymer during biodegradation/enzymatic hydrolysis. *Water Research*, 211, 118068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.118068>
- Witzig, C., Földi, C., Wörle, K., Habermehl, P., Pittroff, M., Müller, Y., Lauschke, T., Fiener, P., Dierkes, G., Freier, K., & Zumbülte, N. (2020). When good intentions go bad—False positive microplastic detection caused by disposable gloves. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 54, 12164–12172. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c03742>
- Wojtyła, C., Zielinska, K., Wojtyła-Buciora, P., & Panek, G. (2020). Prenatal fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) exposure and pregnancy outcomes-analysis of term pregnancies in Poland. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17, 5820. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17165820>